

The Role and Content of Cultural Competence in the Formation of Pedagogical Professional Competence

Abdurakhmanova Sharofat Bakhromaliyevna

Doctoral student of Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature

Abstract. *This article discusses the concept and content of cultural competence. The importance of the cultural approach and its role in the formation of the professional competence of today's literature teachers have been expressed. Different and important aspects of new pedagogical technology from other pedagogical approaches will be highlighted on the basis of examples.*

Key words: *cultural competence, professional competence, cultural approach, innovation, pedagogical thinking, innovative approach, personal culture, literary context, adequate, modeling.*

In today's developing global environment, the concept of a developing person is expanding its essence more and more. In particular, this situation is evident when the term cultural competence is being used in the modern education system along with the qualities of professional competence of specialists. How do we imagine the ideal image of a modern professional today? "The holistic image of a specialist is a cultured person, free, spiritually rich, creative self-awareness, moral self-regulation and the ability to adapt to a changing socio-cultural environment," he says. emphasizes V. Medvedova.

When assessing the changes in the social relations of any nation, one directly refers to the past related to the socio-cultural history of that nation, which, in turn, from the students of the school who learn it, along with the national culture of these nations, as well as universal human culture it requires to study the aspects related to it in parallel. In such conditions, a new approach is felt, which serves to round up the pedagogical process and paves the way for the improvement of the field of pedagogical thinking. Culturological education, which is one of the new pedagogical innovations, is useful in uncovering the basis of the problems we recognized above and in deep and accurate analysis of sources related to the rich cultural history of nations. S.N. Batrakova says about the culturological approach: "This approach is developing in the context and direction of the development of modern science and culture, which directly implies changes in human consciousness and thinking. The cultural approach to the understanding of the pedagogical process is not a matter of new techniques, but primarily a type of approach related to the worldview of the teacher, his methodological understanding of pedagogical realities, and his professional formation and development. The true essence of the cultural approach is a pedagogical process aimed at uncovering the basis of universal knowledge about humanity, and it is not a mistake to look at it as the most convenient means of studying a person, his being and his existence.

The cultural approach aims to study the spiritual and aesthetic impact of the rich life experience, cultural heritage and artistic appeal of the people being studied in the course of the students' education in various subjects. In this situation, it is necessary for a science teacher to have cultural competence along with knowledge and professional ability.

The use of the cultural approach in the educational system allows students to learn the interdependence and differences in the comparison of the culture, lifestyle, customs and traditions of other nations with the culture of their own people, and to use them in a large area. - by studying in a broad socio-historical context, it is intended to understand the essence of the artistic creation and to feel the elegant charm of existence through this meaning, thereby opening the way to the formation of a spiritually mature person.

"Cultural competence is the integrative quality of the teacher's personality, adequate perception of artistic works, the ability to independently assess them, the ability to use spiritual and educational abilities" [Medvedova V. 21].

This competence is a pedagogical ability aimed at the ability of the literature teacher to be aware of the national and socio-cultural identity of the studied people, to be able to reveal the individual characteristics of this people and to convey their artistic appeal to the students.

"Using the cultural approach, - says cultural scientist I. Khodyakova, - moral and aesthetic education of schoolchildren, development of their creative abilities, formation of worldview and development of personality qualities." Therefore, the cultural approach is important in the formation of the spiritual and cultural image of people in addition to revealing the cultural aspects of fiction. Also, it not only serves to increase the effectiveness of the teacher's cognitive assessment in the system of pedagogical activity, but also opens the way to the unification of the teacher-student cooperation relationship and the more active manifestation of spiritual quality in the pedagogical process.

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